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Confluence of Research, Theory and Practice in the
Built Environment

EDITORS

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EVALUATING THE ENVIRONMENTAL CONSEQUENCES OF DIGITAL INTEGRATION IN CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The construction industry is experiencing a profound shift due to the integration of digital technologies, which are altering the way projects are conceptualised, designed, managed, and executed. However, the environmental impact of this digital integration in Nigerian construction projects remains unclear. This study assessed these environmental consequences using a quantitative approach, distributing close-ended questionnaires to professionals, including architects, builders, engineers, and quantity surveyors. The data were analysed using statistical tools such as percentages, frequencies, mean scores, and factor analysis. The results identified five key consequences: energy efficiency, sustainable resource use, reduced material consumption, resource extraction for technology, and electronic waste management. Four categories emerged from the analysis: energy and carbon dynamics, material and resource management, waste and recycling, and environmental compliance and impact mitigation. The findings indicate that the environmental consequences of digital integration in Nigerian construction projects are significant. This study provides crucial insights for industry leaders, enabling more informed decisions on adopting digital technologies to mitigate negative environmental impacts.

Keywords: Environmental consequences, Carbon emissions, Digital technologies, Construction projects, Sustainable communities.

INTRODUCTION

The integration of digital technologies in construction projects has introduced innovative processes, transforming activities, operations, and project timelines (Rachmawati and Kim, 2022). While the construction industry benefits from the Fourth Industrial Revolution, it faces significant environmental consequences from the implementation and use of digital technologies (Agustí-Juan and Habert, 2017). These technologies include the Internet of Things (IoT), Big Data analytics, 3D printing, autonomous robots, Artificial Intelligence (AI),

Augmented Reality Technology (ART), Building Information Modeling (BIM), Virtual Reality (VR), Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), and other emerging tools (Kineber *et al.* 2023). In addition to helping construction organisations remain agile and competitive, the adoption of digital technologies enhances decision-making processes and improves project efficiency and productivity (Oke *et al.* 2023). However, widespread adoption also introduces challenges, such as a shortened lifespan for devices, which leads to electronic waste and requires responsible disposal and recycling of obsolete hardware (Li *et al.* 2022). The increased use of energy-intensive tools contributes to a larger carbon footprint, especially when powered by non-renewable energy sources (Huo *et al.* 2023). The manufacturing of these digital tools involves the extraction of metals and minerals, contributing to environmental degradation and habitat disruption (Aliu and Oke, 2023). Implementing sustainable sourcing practices is, therefore, essential to mitigate these environmental impacts. One major concern is the disposal and management of electronic waste in construction projects. Improper handling of e-waste poses serious environmental threats, leading to pollution and potential health hazards (Hou *et al.* 2023). Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive understanding of the entire lifecycle of digital technologies in construction, focusing on responsible sourcing, sustainable manufacturing, and eco-friendly disposal methods (Wu *et al.* 2023; Thanh *et al.* 2023). This study is unique in its focus on the specific environmental impacts of digital integration within the Nigerian context, a gap often overlooked in existing literature.

While previous research has primarily explored the economic and operational benefits of digital integration (Aliu and Oke, 2023), digital technology adoption (Kineber *et al.* 2023), and barriers to their application (Oke *et al.* 2023; Oke *et al.* 2024), this study addresses environmental implications such as energy consumption, waste reduction, and resource optimisation. The findings will contribute to sustainable construction practices in Nigeria, offering insights to guide policymakers and industry stakeholders towards more environmentally conscious digital integration. This study's originality lies in its focus on bridging the gap between digital innovation and environmental sustainability in Nigerian construction, providing a distinct contribution by addressing underexplored environmental impacts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Impact of Modern Digital Tools on Environmental Sustainability in Nigerian Construction

Modern digital tools greatly enhance environmental sustainability in Nigeria's construction sector (Oke *et al.* 2023). Leveraging Building Information Modelling (BIM) allows project managers to optimise material usage, thereby reducing waste and resource consumption (Abolore, 2012). Drones and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) provide precise site analysis, minimising environmental disruption (Thanh *et al.* 2023). Advanced simulation software promotes energy-efficient designs, leading to buildings with reduced carbon footprints (Rachmawati and Kim, 2022). Additionally, digital tools enable real-time monitoring of construction activities, ensuring compliance with environmental regulations (Kineber *et al.* 2023). These innovations not only reduce the environmental impact of construction projects but also contribute to the development of sustainable infrastructure, aligning with global sustainability goals and fostering greener urban development in Nigeria (Umoh *et al.* 2024).

Environmental Consequences of Digital Integration in the Construction Industry

The integration of digital tools in the construction industry has led to significant environmental benefits. Chief among these is the reduction of material waste, with tools like BIM and precision software enhancing planning and execution accuracy, thus minimising waste generation (Agustí-Juan and Habert, 2017). Optimised processes have also contributed to lowering carbon emissions, improving efficiency and reducing the carbon footprint of construction activities (Wu *et al.* 2023). Energy-efficient designs and management tools further enhance building performance (Thanh *et al.* 2023). Digital tracking promotes sustainable resource management, ensuring responsible use of materials (Hui *et al.* 2023), while efficient monitoring systems help reduce water consumption during construction. Digital integration also facilitates the recycling and reuse of materials (Oke *et al.* 2023; Oke and Aliu, 2024), and improved environmental compliance through digital means reduces non-compliance risks (Abikoye *et al.* 2024). However, digital integration is not without its drawbacks. The energy consumption associated with digital tools and data centres can increase overall energy use, potentially offsetting some environmental benefits (Abolore, 2012). The rise in electronic devices has also led to increased electronic waste, creating disposal challenges (Rachmawati and Kim, 2022). Resource-intensive production processes, including the extraction of rare earth metals used in these tools, have negative environmental impacts (Umoh *et al.* 2024; Cherepovitsyn *et al.* 2023). Data centres contribute to a considerable carbon footprint, and the lifecycle environmental costs of digital devices, from production to disposal, exacerbate the overall impact (Oke *et al.* 2024; Wu *et al.* 2023). Additionally, while digital tools optimise processes, inefficient management may result in increased overall energy consumption (Thanh *et al.* 2023).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study rigorously evaluated the environmental consequences of digital integration in Nigerian construction projects. A comprehensive literature review was conducted, analysing fourteen environmental consequences from sources indexed in Scopus and Web of Science, focusing on themes such as ‘environmental impact,’ ‘degradation,’ and ‘digital integration.’ A post-positivist approach was adopted, using quantitative methods to collect data from experienced construction professionals in Lagos State, Nigeria. Lagos was chosen as the study location due to its status as a major urban centre and the construction hub of the country, with numerous ongoing construction projects that integrate digital technologies (Auwalu and Bello, 2023). The study specifically targeted architects, builders, engineers, and quantity surveyors. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire designed to measure the environmental consequences of digital integration in construction projects. A five-point Likert scale was employed, where 1 represented ‘Strongly Disagree’ and 5 represented ‘Strongly Agree.’

The threshold adopted for the Mean Item Score (MIS) was 3.4, based on the work of Velasco (2015), ensuring a clear benchmark for evaluating the significance of respondents’ views. The population of 3,491 construction professionals was derived from professional bodies such as the Nigerian Institute of Architects (NIA), the Nigerian Society of Engineers (NSE), the Nigerian Institute of Building (NIOB), and the Nigerian Institute of Quantity Surveyors (NIQS). Using the Yamane equation, the sample size was calculated to be 185. However, due to time and resource constraints, a convenience sampling technique was employed. Out of 185 distributed questionnaires, 127 (68.6%) were retrieved and used for analysis. The retrieved sample size provided a reliable dataset for assessing the environmental impact of digital integration.

The questionnaire’s validity was ensured through face and content validation by 15 experts, while its reliability was confirmed with a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.958, indicating high internal consistency. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS, with Mean Item Scores (MIS) and factor analysis being the key analytical tools. The MIS was used to summarise respondents’ opinions on various environmental consequences, while factor analysis identified the underlying dimensions, grouping related variables into key factors. These techniques provided insight into the most significant environmental impacts of digital integration in construction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Background Information of Respondents

This section presents an overview of the respondents’ profiles for the research. The findings indicate that engineers, encompassing mechanical, electrical, and civil disciplines, constituted the largest group, representing 36.2% of participants. Quantity surveyors followed at 23.6%, while architects accounted for 20.5%. Builders were the least represented, making up 19.7% of the total sample, as detailed in Table 1. Regarding work experience within the construction industry, 29.9% of respondents reported having at least five years, 38.6% had a minimum of ten years, and 18.9% had up to fifteen years of experience. Additionally, Table 1 highlights that the majority of respondents held a Bachelor’s degree (B.Tech/BSc), representing 36.2% of the total, followed by Master’s degree holders (M.Tech/MSc) at 30.7%, diploma holders at 18.1%, and those with a PhD at 16.5%.

Table 1: Respondent’s Demographics

Category of the Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Academic Qualification of Respondents		
(HND) Higher national diploma	23	18.1
(B/Tech/BSc) Bachelor’s degree	46	36.2
(M/Tech/MSc) Master’s degree	39	30.7
(PhD) Doctor of Philosophy	21	16.5
Total	127	100
Profession of respondents		
Architect	26	20.5
Engineers (Mechanical, Electrical, Civil)	46	36.2
Builders	25	19.7
Quantity Surveyor	30	23.6
Total	127	100
Years of experience		
1-5 years	38	29.9
6-10 years	49	38.6
10-15 years	24	18.9
16-20 years	9	7.1
Above 21 years	7	5.5
Total	127	100

Environmental Consequences of Digital Integration in the Construction Industry

This study identified fourteen environmental consequences of digital integration from the reviewed literature, employing mean score and factor analysis. The results from Table 2 indicated that energy efficiency, sustainable resource management, reduced material usage, resource extraction for technology, and electronic waste management are the most significant

environmental consequences of digital integration in the construction industry. Conversely, the carbon footprint of data centres and reduced water consumption do not significantly impact the Nigerian construction industry, as their scores fell below the 3.4 threshold established by Velasco.

The findings of this study align with recent research highlighting energy efficiency and sustainable resource management as crucial benefits of digital integration in construction (Khan *et al.* 2021; Elshaer *et al.* 2022). However, they contrast with studies by Zuo *et al.* (2020) and Adnan *et al.* (2023), which identified significant impacts of data centre carbon footprints and water consumption in other regions. This divergence suggests that the environmental consequences of digital integration may vary significantly by context, emphasising the need for region-specific assessments in evaluating digital strategies in construction.

Table 2: Ranking of Environmental Consequences of Digital Integration

Environmental Consequences	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
Energy Efficiency	4.24	1.453	1
Sustainable resource management	4.07	0.564	2
Reduced materials waste	3.93	0.876	3
Resource extraction for technology	3.87	0.743	4
Electronic waste management	3.82	2.771	5
Lower carbon emission	3.67	0.654	6
Improved environmental compliance	3.67	0.871	7
Increase recycling and reuse	3.61	1.321	8
Increased demand for rare earth metals	3.58	1.654	9
Lifecycle environmental cost of technology	3.51	0.432	10
Energy consumption in digital tools	3.48	0.342	11
Potential for increased overall energy use	3.41	0.216	12
Datacenter Carbon footprint	3.24	0.765	13
Reduced water consumption	3.17	1.095	14

After confirming the factorability of the variables, a comprehensive factor analysis was conducted. As illustrated in Table 3, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure yielded a value of 0.823, accompanied by a significant p-value of 0.000 for the Bartlett test of sphericity. According to Tabachnick *et al.* (2007), this KMO value surpasses the minimum threshold of 0.6, suggesting that the variables are suitable for factor analysis.

Table 3: The Factor Analysis of the Fourteen Variables

KMO measure of sampling adequacy		0.823
Barlett's test of sphericity	Approximate chi-square	3463.654
	Df	435
	Sig	0.000

Environmental Consequences	1	2	3	4
Cluster1: Energy and Carbon Dynamics				
Energy consumption in digital tools	0.843	–	–	–
Data center carbon footprint	0.797	–	–	–
Potential for increased overall energy use	0.744	–	–	–
Energy efficiency	0.714	–	–	–
Cluster 2: Material and Resource Management				
Sustainable resource management	–	0.798	–	–
Reduced material waste	–	0.758	–	–
Resource extraction for technology	–	0.742	–	–

Increased demand for rare earth metals	–	0.738	–	–
Cluster 3: Waste and Recycling Dynamics	–	–	–	–
Electronic waste generation	–	–	0.756	–
Increased recycling and reuse	–	–	0.733	–
Reduced water consumption	–	–	0.704	–
Cluster4: Environmental Compliance and Impact Mitigation	–	–	–	–
Life cycle environmental Cost of Technology	–	–	–	0.775
Lower carbon emissions	–	–	–	0.744
Improved environmental compliance	–	–	–	0.714

Discussion of Clusters

The primary objective of this research is to assess the environmental consequences of digital integration in construction projects in Nigeria. This study aims to provide rigorous insights into sustainable practices and support the development of environmentally friendly strategies within the construction sector. The analysis revealed four clusters, with “Material and Resource Management” being the most significant, with an average mean score of 3.86. The discussion of each cluster is provided below, emphasising the insights from previous studies and their comparisons with this study’s outcomes.

Cluster 1: Energy and Carbon Dynamics

The first cluster, “Energy and Carbon Dynamics,” consists of four variables: ‘energy consumption in digital tools’, ‘data centre carbon footprint’, ‘potential for increased overall energy use’, and ‘energy efficiency discussion’. This cluster underscores the importance of managing energy consumption and carbon emissions resulting from digital integration. Previous studies, such as those by Song *et al.* (2023) and Thanh *et al.* (2023), indicate that while digital tools can enhance energy efficiency, their implementation can also lead to increased energy demand if not optimised effectively. These findings align with the results of this study, emphasising the need for careful energy management in digital integration to minimise environmental impacts.

Cluster 2: Material and Resource Management

The second cluster, “Material and Resource Management,” is the most significant, with an average mean score of 3.86. It encompasses four variables: ‘sustainable resource use’, ‘reduced material waste’, ‘resource extraction for technology’, and ‘increased demand for rare earth metals’. This cluster highlights the dual benefits and challenges associated with digital integration. On the one hand, digital tools can optimise resource allocation and reduce material waste, as noted by (Hui *et al.* 2023). On the other hand, the increasing demand for rare earth metals poses significant environmental concerns, including habitat destruction and pollution, as outlined by (Putra *et al.* 2023). Comparative studies, such as Iwugbu *et al.*(2023) in Nigeria and Liu *et al.* (2024) in China, corroborate these findings, demonstrating that while digital integration can facilitate sustainable resource management, it simultaneously raises concerns about the environmental costs of resource extraction. These studies emphasise the necessity for the construction industry to balance the advantages of reduced waste with the environmental impacts of sourcing materials for digital technologies.

Cluster 3: Waste and Recycling Dynamics

The third cluster, “Waste and Recycling Dynamics,” includes three variables: ‘electronic waste generation’, ‘increased recycling and reuse’, and ‘reduced water consumption’. This cluster focuses on the implications of digital integration on waste management and resource conservation. The generation of electronic waste is a growing concern due to the toxic materials present in electronics, as highlighted by (Ghulam and Abushammala, 2023). However, opportunities for increased recycling and reuse can mitigate the environmental footprint, as noted by (Talla and Mellwaine, 2024). The findings from this study align with these observations, reinforcing the importance of implementing effective waste management strategies to support a circular economy in the construction industry.

Cluster 4: Environmental Compliance and Impact Mitigation

The last cluster, “Environmental Compliance and Impact Mitigation,” comprises three variables: ‘life cycle environmental costs of technology’, ‘lower carbon emissions’, and ‘improved environmental compliance’. This cluster addresses the broader environmental impacts and compliance aspects of digital integration. Effective management of life cycle environmental costs is critical to ensuring that digital tools contribute positively to sustainability goals, as indicated by (Wolf *et al.* 2023). Moreover, the enhancements in environmental compliance through improved monitoring and reporting mechanisms facilitate adherence to regulatory standards, as highlighted by (Abikoye *et al.* 2024).

The insights gained from this research not only highlight the challenges faced by the construction industry in balancing the benefits and costs of digital integration but also situate these findings within the broader context of existing literature. This study contributes significantly to the discourse on sustainable practices in the construction sector, emphasising the need for a holistic approach that considers both the advantages and challenges posed by digital technologies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

As the construction sector increasingly adopts digital integration to enhance productivity and project outcomes, it is essential to evaluate the environmental impacts of these technologies. This study identifies energy efficiency, sustainable resource use, reduced material consumption, resource extraction for technology, and electronic waste management as the most significant environmental consequences of digital integration within the Nigerian construction industry. In contrast, the carbon footprint of data centres and reduced water consumption were found to have minimal impact on construction projects. The study categorised the fourteen environmental consequences into four distinct clusters: Energy and Carbon Dynamics, Material and Resource Management, Waste and Recycling Dynamics, and Environmental Compliance and Impact Mitigation. Notably, the second cluster, Material and Resource Management, emerged as the most significant, highlighting the importance of sustainable resource practices in digital integration.

To mitigate the adverse effects of resource depletion, energy consumption, and emissions, the study recommends that the Nigerian construction industry prioritise the adoption of energy-efficient and recyclable digital tools. Additionally, it is crucial to advocate for the Nigerian government to develop comprehensive regulatory frameworks that mandate environmental

compliance and life cycle assessments for digital technologies, ensuring their integration aligns with national sustainability goals. Furthermore, future research should explore the long-term impacts of digital integration on environmental sustainability in construction, focusing on the effectiveness of specific strategies identified in this study. Investigating how emerging technologies can further reduce environmental consequences will also be valuable. By aligning recommendations with the findings of this study, subsequent research can contribute to a more sustainable construction industry in Nigeria.

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